

2-Hydroxy-4-Methylbenzophenoneoxime as Analytical Reagent : Gravimetric Determination of Copper

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2-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzophenone oxime (HMBOX) has been used as a reagent for gravimetric estimation of copper and for its separation from other ions. Copper is quantitatively precipitated by HMBOX at pH 3.0-8.0. After drying the precipitate at 110-120°, its composition corresponds to the formula $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$. Interference due to Fe(III) has been eliminated by masking with potassium tartrate and in other cases by suitable control of pH. Copper and nickel were estimated in different alloys.

MANY oximes have been used as analytical reagents for gravimetric determination of a number of metal ions. Salicylaldoxime¹⁻³, resacetophenone oxime⁴⁻⁵ and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime⁶⁻⁹ have already been reported as analytical reagents for copper. 2-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzophenone oxime (HMBOX)¹⁰ has been successfully employed for the gravimetric determination of nickel, its separation from a number of ions and determination of nickel and copper in their binary mixture.

The present work with the reagent HMBOX was undertaken with the intention to introduce a new ligand for the gravimetric determination of copper. HMBOX gives buff precipitate with copper at pH range 3.0 to 8.0.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by using copper chloride and standardised. Solutions of other ions were prepared from their salts. An ethanolic solution of the reagent was employed and pH was adjusted using acetic acid and sodium acetate.

Synthesis of the reagent :

2-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzophenoneoxime was prepared by the reaction of 2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzophenone with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide (40%) in dilute ethanol. It crystallised from petroleum as colourless needles, m.p. 106°. A 1% reagent solution was prepared by dissolving the oxime in ethanol.

Determination of copper :

An aliquot of standard copper chloride solution containing 3-48 mg copper taken in a beaker was diluted to about 150 ml and pH was adjusted using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. The solution was warmed to 60° and 1% ethanolic solution of the reagent was added with constant stirring till it was 1% excess over the calculated amount. The buff precipitate of copper complex was digested on a

water bath at about 60-70° and allowed to stand for 30 min. It was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G 4), washed with hot water followed by 40% ethanol to remove excess reagent, dried at 110-120° to constant weight and finally weighed as $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$. It was found that copper can be quantitatively determined at pH range 3.0-8.0. Conversion factor for copper(II) is 0.1233. The results of some of the estimations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COPPER
pH 3.0-3.5

Copper taken (mg)	Copper complex (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Error (mg)
3.14	25.6	3.16	+0.02
6.28	50.7	6.25	-0.03
15.70	127.0	15.66	-0.04
31.40	255.0	31.44	+0.04
47.10	383.0	47.22	+0.12

Precision and accuracy :

The relative standard deviation in the determination of copper (15.70 mg) by the given method was $\pm 0.4\%$ in 15 determinations.

Determination of copper in presence of foreign ions :

To study the effect of foreign ions on gravimetric determination of copper, 8-16 mg of various cations were added to a known volume of copper solution (15.70 mg copper) at pH 3.0-3.5 and estimations were carried out as mentioned above. It was observed that Pb(II), Cd(II), Al(III), Zn(II), Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Ba(II), Sr(II), Ca(II) and Mg(II) do not interfere in the gravimetric determination of copper.

The reagent reacts with Ni(II) at pH 5.0 giving green coloured precipitate, with Co(II) at pH 6.0 giving yellow precipitate and with Fe(III) at pH 2.6 giving blue-violet colouration. Since Ni(II) and Co(II) start precipitating at higher pH, Cu(II) can

be determined in presence of these ions by working at controlled pH. Presence of Fe(III) interferes with the determination of Cu(II); the determination, however, was carried out by sequestering the Fe(III) by potassium tartrate.

Separation and determination of copper and nickel :

Definite volume of standard solutions of copper(II) and nickel(II) were mixed together and diluted to 200 ml, pH was adjusted to 3.0-3.5. The buff copper chelate precipitated on adding ethanolic solution of the reagent was estimated gravimetrically as above. The filtrate and washings after removal of copper chelate were collected for the estimation of nickel. The volume was reduced to about 100 ml by heating. Its pH was adjusted to 5.5 and nickel was estimated as described earlier¹⁰. The results are reproducible with an error $\pm 0.4\%$ for 3.0-16.0 mg copper.

Determination of copper and nickel in alloys :

Copper and nickel have also been accurately determined in different alloys like brass (Cu, 61.25; Zn, 38.75%), bronze (Cu, 87.26; Sn, 8.42; Pb, 1.96; Zn, 1.20%), cupro-nickel (Cu, 68.20; Ni, 30.45; Fe, 0.15%), german silver (Cu, 56.0; Zn, 20.0; Ni, 8.0; Pb, 7.0; Fe, 5.0%) at the above pH values and percentage of copper and nickel obtained in different alloys agree with the reported values within the experimental error.

For the estimation of copper and nickel in alloys 0.5-0.6 g of the alloy was dissolved in conc. nitric acid, digested on a water bath for 1 hr and evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water. If the sample contained tin, metastannic acid was filtered off and washed with dil. HNO₃. The filtrate and washings were collected and made upto 250 ml. 10-15 ml of this solution was used to determine copper/nickel. Copper was determined in the solution at pH 3.0 as described above and nickel was then estimated in the filtrate (after the removal of copper) by raising the pH to 5.5-6.5. If the sample contained iron, it was masked by adding potassium tartrate before adding the reagent.

Determination of metal content in the complex :

The copper 2-hydroxy-4-methylbenzophenone oxime complex (1 g) was decomposed with conc.

nitric acid and excess of nitric acid expelled by evaporation with conc. sulphuric acid. The residue was cooled and carefully digested with water, filtered and made upto 100 ml in a volumetric flask. The copper content of this solution was determined iodometrically and was found to be 12.28% (Calcd. : 12.33%) in agreement with the proposed formula Cu(C₁₄H₁₂O₂N)₂.

Results and Discussion

The gravimetric results showed a maximum error of $\pm 0.65\%$ in the determination of 3-48 mg copper(II) and demonstrated that the precipitate can be dried to constant weight. As the molecular weight of the complex is high (conversion factor 0.1233), very small amount of copper can be determined with considerable accuracy. The reagent has no tendency to coprecipitate with copper complex and the precipitate is heavy and easy to filter off. The oxime can be prepared in a high state of purity.

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